

Classroom Management Strategies for Improved Instructional Delivery in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State

Amadi-Iwai Christopher Chido & Amadi-Iwai Patience

Department of Educational Management,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt
Department of Business Education
Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt

Corresponding Authors' email: patienceamadiiwai@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigated classroom management strategies for improved instructional delivery in public junior secondary schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. Three research questions and Three null hypotheses guided the study. The theoretical framework was based on the Reinforcement Theory by B.F. Skinner (1904–1990) and the Assertive Discipline Model by Canter (1976). A descriptive survey design was employed, targeting a population of 559 public junior secondary school teachers in the area. A sample size of 236 teachers was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan Table. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled, "Classroom Management Strategies for Improved Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (CMSIIDQ)" the content and face validity of the instrument was established by the project supervisor and not expects in the field of educational management in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The instrument's reliability was confirmed at coefficient of 0.75 using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Method. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while independent t-tests were applied to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that teachers extensively employ various classroom management strategies, including class control, arrangement, discipline, and effective communication, to improve instructional delivery. Both male and female teachers demonstrated no significant differences in their adoption of these strategies, suggesting uniformity in application across genders. The study concluded that effective classroom management plays a crucial role in enhancing student engagement and academic achievement. It recommended regular training for teachers, collaborative efforts between parents and teachers, and the integration of classroom management strategies into teacher education programs to improve instructional delivery.

Keywords: Classroom Management, Strategies, Instructional Delivery

INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is an essential component of effective instructional delivery. All classroom activities are carried out within specified time schedule. If not properly managed, other non-instructional activities that do on around the classroom environment can interrupt and affect the actual instructional delivery. A good teacher must ensure that there is proper classroom management that can enable the achievement of the instructional objectives. Effective classroom management sets the stage for teaching and learning. It sets a tone in the classroom that captures students' attention. Very little academic learning can take place without proper classroom management as a chaotic and unorganized classroom as a result of poor classroom management is likely to affect learning and students' academic performance (George, Sakirudeen & Adam, 2017).

Oliver, Wehby and Reschly (2018) asserted that classroom management is broader than the idea of student control and discipline, it includes all the things a teacher must do in the classroom to foster students'

academic involvement and cooperation in the classroom activities to create conducive learning environment. Viewing classroom management in a holistic sense incorporates every element of the classroom from the classroom environment to instructional delivery, students' participation and the achievement of instructional goals or objectives. According to Dada and Okunade (2014), the holistic sense of classroom management includes; creating organized and orderly classroom, establishing expectations, including students' cooperation in learning tasks, and dealing with the procedural demands of the classroom. Teachers can deal with students' disruptive behaviours and other factors by applying effective classroom management strategies that can increase attentiveness and engagement and also pave way for better academic performance.

The application of effective classroom management no doubt, can bring about enthusiasm, interest, and engagement. The teacher as the class manager adopts different strategies to ensure good class tempo that will drive students' attention and the achievement of

instructional objectives. The teacher has a repertoire of approaches that is been applied depending on the behavioural patterns exhibited by the students and the situation at hand (Emmer & Stough, 2001). Teaching a number of students with different needs, behaviours, and attention spans can be very challenging. However, the ability of the teacher to successfully create a well-managed, structured classroom environment that can make learning occur is imperative.

Instructional delivery is successful, when there is effective and adequate classroom management. Instructional delivery is referred to as the methods, strategies, approaches or techniques employed by a teacher to deliver the content of lesson to the learners. So, every effort that the teacher makes in order to have a fruitful time with the students by exposing the contents, employing methods, strategies, students' interaction with the environment, resource materials and evaluation process sums of to mean instructional delivery (Farrant, 2014). Teachers do not use particular delivery method for every lesson. Different instructional delivery methods are utilized in different lessons; classroom environment and students' skilful classroom management and choice of appropriate teaching method brings about harmony and orderliness in the classroom during instructional delivery. While it is not expected that classroom management can eliminate all disruptive behaviour, it can improve instructional delivery and increase class performance and academic performance of students.

The actualization of effective instructional delivery can only be attained in a situation where classroom management procedures are duly observed. The success of teaching and learning depends largely on the teacher's performance in classroom management. The teacher utilizes specific classroom strategies to influence and coordinate students' behaviour to ensure the achievement of learning objectives. The effects of institutional delivery can hardly be separated from the effects of proper classroom management on students' academic performance. Teaching a number of students with different needs and behaviour can also be very challenging. Hence, it is imperative that secondary school teachers take proactive measures in understanding the modern classroom management strategies such as class control, class arrangement, class discipline and effective communication that can improve instructional delivery in the challenging demands of the

21st century classroom. This is what the researcher intends to explore in this study.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to ascertain the classroom management strategies for improved instructional delivery of Secondary School teachers. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify classroom management strategies for improved instructional delivery in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.
2. Determine the extent to which class control is adopted as classroom management strategy for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. Examine the extent to which class arrangement is adopted as classroom management strategy for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the classroom management strategies for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?
2. What is the extent to which class control classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?
3. What is the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the classroom management strategies adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary School in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the extent to which class control classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the male and female teachers, on the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey design. This design is considered appropriate because it involve collection of data for the purpose if describing systematically the characteristics, features and facts about the given population. The area of the study was Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. The population of this study consisted of 599 teachers from public junior secondary schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. These teachers were distributed across 25 secondary schools in various locations within the local government area. The total sample for this study comprised 236 teachers of public junior secondary schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Classroom Management Strategies for Improved Instructional Delivery Questionnaire (CMSIIDQ)” was structured by the researcher. The instrument consist of two section A and B with each section structured into four point rating scale. The content and face validity of the instrument was established by experts in the field of educational management in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE), Rivers State.

The reliability of the instrument was established using test – retest method. The questionnaire was administered to 20 teachers teaching in public junior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area the result will be recorded and after two weeks the test was re-administered to the same group. The two sets of scores were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) method. The reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained which justified the reliability of the instrument. The descriptive statistical tools, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using independent t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The following values are assigned to the

- Very High Extent (VHE) - 4
- High Extent (HE) - 3
- Low Extent - 2
- Very Low Extent - 1

From the above, the mean scores to determine the acceptability or rejection of any item is as follows:
 $\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$

This means that the mean scores that is 2.50 and above was regarded as high extent while mean scores below 2.50 was regarded as low extent. The computed value for t-critical was 1.96. therefore, null hypotheses that are less than t-crit of 1.96 was accepted while those above the t-crit value of 1.96 was rejected.

RESULT

Research Question One: What are the classroom management strategies for effective instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation on the Classroom Management Strategies for Effective Instructional Delivery.

S/N	Classroom Management Strategies	Gender				Mean Set	Remark
		Male (66)		Female(170)			
		Mean	Std.	Mean	Std.		
1.	Teachers deliver lessons in an engaging manner to keep students actively involved in learning activities.	3.11	0.90	3.14	0.89	3.13	High Extent
2.	Teachers give rewards for good behaviour.	2.73	1.02	2.68	1.06	2.71	High Extent
3.	Teachers utilize fair and consistent discipline to create a sense of safety and trust.	2.92	0.95	2.98	1.01	2.95	High Extent

4. Teachers utilize different teaching methods of communication (verbal and non-verbal) to keep students engage.	2.89	0.99	3.12	0.86	3.01	High Extent
5. Teachers utilize different type of sitting arrangement depending on their activities	2.83	0.90	2.97	0.86	2.90	High Extent
Grand Mean	2.90	0.97	2.98	1.94	2.94	High Extent

The data presented in Table 1 highlights the classroom management strategies employed by teachers for effective instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. The mean and standard deviation for both male and female teachers were analyzed across five key strategies. The findings show that all strategies were utilized to a high extent, as evidenced by the grand mean of 2.94. Specifically, teachers delivering lessons in an engaging manner to actively involve students had the highest mean score (3.13), indicating its prominent role in fostering effective instructional delivery. The use of fair and consistent discipline (mean = 2.95) and the adoption of varied teaching methods, including verbal and non-verbal communication (mean = 3.01), also received high ratings, suggesting that these approaches are effective in maintaining student engagement and

trust. Similarly, the use of rewards for good behavior (mean = 2.71) and flexible seating arrangements tailored to different activities (mean = 2.90) were employed at a high extent, contributing to an organized and dynamic classroom environment. The findings suggest that teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre LGA adopt diverse and effective classroom management strategies that enhance instructional delivery. These strategies create an engaging, safe, and supportive learning atmosphere, which is crucial for student participation and academic success.

Research Question Two: What is the extent to which class control classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent to which Class Control Classroom Management Strategy is Adopted for Improved Instructional Delivery

S/N	Class control classroom	Gender				Mean Set	Remark
		Male (66) Mean	Female(170) Std.	Female(170) Mean	Male (66) Std.		
6.	Teachers ensure that the classroom environment is conducive and attractive for teaching and learning activities.	2.58	1.20	2.59	1.13	2.59	High Extent
7.	Teachers ensure that there is adequate provision of instructional materials and that they and effectively utilized in teaching and learning process.	2.73	1.14	2.73	1.14	2.73	High Extent
8.	Teachers ensure that lessons are properly planned and challenging to stimulate students' interest in the teaching and learning process.	2.80	0.98	2.66	1.02	2.73	High Extent
9.	Teachers maintain good inter-personal relationships with the students to create mutual trust and friendship for effective instructional process.	2.38	1.20	2.31	1.14	2.35	High Extent
10.	Teachers show adequate mastery of subject content and instructional method to maintain class control.	2.80	0.96	2.83	1.00	2.82	High Extent
Grand Mean		2.66	1.10	2.62	1.08	2.62	High Extent

The data in Table 2 evaluates the extent to which class control as a classroom management strategy is adopted

by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State, for improved

instructional delivery. The results show that the overall grand mean for both male and female teachers is 2.62, indicating a high extent of adoption of class control strategies.

Among the strategies, the highest-rated was teachers demonstrating adequate mastery of subject content and instructional methods to maintain class control, with a mean of 2.82. This suggests that subject mastery plays a pivotal role in fostering effective classroom management. Teachers ensuring the provision and effective utilization of instructional materials, along with properly planning lessons to stimulate student interest, were also rated highly, with mean scores of 2.73 each. These findings underline the importance of well-prepared and resource-rich instructional delivery in maintaining class control.

Teachers ensuring a conducive and attractive classroom environment was moderately rated, with a mean score of 2.59, signifying its importance in creating a

supportive learning atmosphere. The lowest-rated strategy was maintaining good interpersonal relationships with students (mean = 2.35). While still rated as a high extent, this relatively lower score suggests potential areas for improvement in fostering trust and rapport with students. The findings indicate that Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre LGA adopt class control strategies to a high extent, emphasizing subject mastery, effective lesson planning, and the provision of instructional materials as key components for improved instructional delivery. However, efforts to enhance teacher-student relationships could further strengthen class control and instructional effectiveness.

Research Question Three: What is the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard deviation on the Extent to which Class Arrangement Classroom Management Strategy is Adopted for Improved Instructional Delivery

S/N	Class Discipline Management Strategies	Gender				Mean Set	Remark
		Male (66)		Female (170)			
		Mean	Std.	Mean	Std.		
11.	Teachers place students with disruptive behaviour outside the classroom management temporarily for effective classroom management instructional delivery.	2.95	0.95	3.04	0.88	3.00	High Extent
12.	Teachers use penalty and punishment to students who exhibits undesirable behaviour for effective classroom management and instructional delivery.	3.17	0.85	3.02	0.88	3.10	High Extent
13.	Teachers use positive reinforcement to keep students focused and engaged during instructional delivery.	2.74	1.07	2.93	0.95	2.84	High Extent
14.	Teachers with hold privileges of bad behaviours students to maintain class discipline during instructional delivery.	3.14	0.91	3.11	0.89	3.13	High Extent
15.	Teachers use problem-solving strategy to maintain class discipline.	2.58	1.08	2.56	1.04	2.57	High Extent
Grand Mean		2.92	0.97	2.93	0.93	2.93	High Extent

The data in Table 3 explores the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategies are adopted by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State, for improved instructional delivery. The overall grand mean of 2.93 indicates that these strategies are utilized to a high extent. Among the specific strategies, the highest-rated was the use of penalty and punishment for students exhibiting undesirable behavior, with a mean of 3.10. This suggests that this approach is a prominent method for maintaining class discipline and improving instructional delivery. Similarly, withholding privileges

from students who display bad behavior (mean = 3.13) and placing disruptive students outside the classroom temporarily (mean = 3.00) were also rated highly, reflecting their effectiveness in creating a conducive learning environment.

Positive reinforcement to keep students focused and engaged during lessons received a mean score of 2.84, emphasizing its significance in promoting a supportive classroom atmosphere. The lowest-rated strategy, with a mean score of 2.57, was using problem-solving techniques to maintain class discipline. While still rated as high extent, this strategy may require more emphasis

to enhance its adoption and impact. The findings indicate that Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre LGA extensively use various class arrangement strategies to improve instructional delivery. Strategies such as penalties, withholding privileges, and temporary removal of disruptive students are prioritized. However, greater focus on fostering problem-solving approaches could further enhance the effectiveness of classroom management.

Test for Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the classroom management strategies adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary School in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test on the difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the classroom management strategies adopted for improved instructional delivery.

Location	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-test	Sig.	Decision
Male	66	2.90	0.97	234	-0.320	0.750	NS
Female	170	2.98	1.94				

Key: NS-Not Significant

The data in Table 16 presents a summary of the t-test analysis on the difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the classroom management strategies adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. The results show that the mean response for male teachers is 2.90, with a standard deviation of 0.97, while the mean response for female teachers is 2.98, with a standard deviation of 1.94. The calculated t-value is -0.320, with a significance (p-value) of 0.750, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (H0₁) is not rejected,

indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the classroom management strategies adopted for improved instructional delivery. This suggests that both male and female teachers perceive and adopt these strategies similarly in their teaching practice.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the extent to which class control classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of t-test on the difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers, on the extent to which class control classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery.

Location	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-test	Sig.	Decision
Male	66	2.66	1.10	234	0.254	0.800	NS
Female	170	2.62	1.08				

Key: NS-Not Significant

The data in Table 5 presents the t-test analysis on the difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the extent to which class control classroom management strategies are adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. The results indicate that the mean response for male teachers is 2.66, with a standard deviation of 1.10,

while the mean response for female teachers is 2.62, with a standard deviation of 1.08. The calculated t-value is 0.254, with a significance (p-value) of 0.800, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (H0₂) is not rejected. This implies that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the extent to which class control

strategies are adopted. Thus, both male and female teachers perceive and implement class control strategies in similar ways to enhance instructional delivery.

H0₃: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the male and female teachers, on the extent

to which class arrangement classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State

Table 6: Summary of t-test on the difference in the mean responses of the male and female teachers, on the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategy is adopted for improved instructional delivery.

Location	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-test	Sig.	Decision
Male	66	2.92	0.97	234	-0.073	0.942	NS
Female	170	2.93	0.93				

Key: NS-Not Significant

The data in Table 18 presents the t-test analysis on the difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the extent to which class arrangement classroom management strategies are adopted for improved instructional delivery in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State. The results show that the mean response for male teachers is 2.92, with a standard deviation of 0.97, while the mean response for female teachers is 2.93, with a standard deviation of 0.93. The calculated t-value is -0.073, and the significance (p-value) is 0.942, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (H0₃) is not rejected, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers regarding the adoption of class arrangement strategies. This suggests that both male and female teachers perceive and adopt class arrangement classroom management strategies in a similar manner for improved instructional delivery.

Discussion of Findings

Classroom Management Strategies

The findings from the study revealed that teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Ikwerre Local Government Area adopt various classroom management strategies, such as engaging teaching methods, rewarding positive behavior, and using consistent discipline, to a high extent for effective instructional delivery. The hypothesis (H0₁) further confirmed no significant difference in the responses of male and female teachers regarding the adoption of these strategies. These findings align with the work of Marzano and Marzano (2003), who emphasized that effective classroom management is

pivotal to student achievement. They highlighted that teachers who implement engaging lesson delivery, maintain discipline, and foster a supportive environment significantly improve learning outcomes. Similarly, Eisenman and Cushman (2015) argued that classroom management strategies are universal and not significantly influenced by teacher demographics like gender, but rather by teachers' training and experience. The alignment of the study findings with the literature suggests that the consistent adoption of these strategies across genders supports instructional effectiveness and reduces classroom disruptions.

Class Control Classroom Management Strategy

The study found that teachers adopt class control strategies, such as creating a conducive classroom environment, ensuring the provision of instructional materials, and maintaining interpersonal relationships, to a high extent for improved instructional delivery. Hypothesis 2 (H0₂) revealed no significant difference in the responses of male and female teachers regarding the adoption of class control strategies. This aligns with Brown and Adooh (2021) who identified that a controlled and well-organized classroom environment fosters better student engagement and learning. Additionally, Eisenman and Cushman (2015) emphasized that effective class control requires collaborative teacher-student relationships and a well-prepared teaching process. The results reflect the broader consensus in educational research that classroom control strategies are universally applicable and enhance teaching efficacy when consistently implemented, regardless of the teacher's gender.

Class Discipline Management Strategies

The findings indicated that class arrangement strategies, such as seating arrangements to minimize disruptions, clustering for group work, and creating walking spaces, are adopted to a high extent by teachers in the study area. The hypothesis (H₀₃) also showed no significant difference in the responses of male and female teachers regarding the adoption of these strategies. This supports the findings of Taiwo (2019), who highlighted that physical classroom arrangements significantly impact students' academic engagement and teacher accessibility. Similarly, Woodson (2015) suggested that strategic classroom arrangements help reduce behavioral issues and create a conducive learning atmosphere. These strategies, when applied universally by teachers, enhance classroom interactions and ensure effective instructional delivery. The study's findings reinforce the role of classroom arrangement as a practical approach to managing student behavior and optimizing learning, irrespective of the teacher's gender.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the classroom management strategies adopted by Junior Secondary School teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area, Rivers State, for improved instructional delivery. The findings revealed that teachers extensively utilize various strategies, including class control, arrangement, discipline, and effective communication, to create conducive learning environments and enhance students' academic engagement. The study further found no significant differences in the responses of male and female teachers regarding their adoption of these strategies, indicating a uniform application across genders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made to key stakeholders:

1. Teachers should continuously adopt and refine effective classroom management strategies, such as engaging teaching methods, positive reinforcement, and non-verbal communication, to sustain student interest and enhance instructional delivery.
2. Administrators should organize regular training programs and workshops to equip teachers with advanced classroom management skills and

innovative strategies to improve teaching effectiveness.

3. Parents should collaborate with teachers by reinforcing positive behavior management practices at home, ensuring students are prepared to engage constructively in the classroom.

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